

Business Plan (Strategic Road Map)

Dr.Mirmiran
Business Services

Powering the Future of Electric Vehicle (EV) Charging: The Ultimate Charging Solution for a Sustainable Tomorrow

Product Category: Strategic Roadmap

Author: Seyed Farzad Mirmiran

Title: Business & Academic Researcher

Institution: Central European University (CEU)

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14037852](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14037852)

Executive Summary

As the electric vehicle (EV) market rapidly grows, one major hurdle remains for drivers—efficient access to reliable charging infrastructure. **Dr. Mirmiran** (or **Investors Company**) offers a transformative solution through a user-centric, data-driven platform that provides real-time information on EV charging stations. By simplifying the charging experience and ensuring compatibility, we aim to be the leading EV charging platform, meeting the needs of a rapidly expanding global market while empowering sustainable transportation initiatives..